

Detecting Anomalies in the Separation Process in a Hydrocyclone Using a Medical PET Scanner

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ABSTRACT

In this study the technique of 'positron emission particle tracking' (PEPT), making use of a Siemens TruePoint PET (positron emission tomography) scanner was applied to detect anomalies in the operation of a hydrocyclone. The 3-D position of a particle was determined every millisecond with high spatial resolution with the help of a verified particle labelling method and a data analysis algorithm developed in our research group. A programming code was developed to locate the hydrocyclone axis and to obtain the particle positions and velocities in cylinder coordinates. The flow anomaly, the 'end of the vortex', as well as the position at which it occurs and the time at which a particle reaches it were identified by comparing and analysing particle paths, in terms of residence time, radial position as a function of axial position, and axial and tangential velocities under different operation conditions.

Keywords Positron emission particle tracking; hydrocyclone; anomaly detection; end of the vortex.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Hydrocyclones

Hydrocyclones are cyclones specially designed for separating mixtures for which liquids constitute the continuous phase (see e.g. Svarovsky, 2000), for instance desanding hydrocyclones are used for solid-liquid separation and deoiling hydrocyclones are used for separating oil and non-oily liquids. The separation principle for cyclones is the same as that for centrifuges, but, unlike centrifuges, the construction of cyclones, as shown in Figure 1 (a), involves no moving parts and the fluid's own rotational motion is caused by the geometry of the cyclone. The mixture enters the cyclone tangentially to the outer wall, swirling along the wall towards the cone apex. The dense phase is subjected to a net 'centrifugal force', flung onto the wall and transported by the downward axial motion in the outer part of the swirl, while the lighter phase enters the inner part of the vortex, turns its axial flow direction, and flows out of the cyclone through the vortex finder.

Hydrocyclones are preferred in numerous circumstances because of, among other things, their simple structures and uncomplicated operation procedure. However, the flow patterns inside cyclones are complex, and it is difficult to observe and identify flow anomalies, if present. This work is dedicated to reveal the abnormal flow behaviors inside a hydrocyclone with the help of a medical PET (positron emission tomography) scanner.

1.2 Process tomography on fault detections of hydrocyclones

Several tomographic methods have been developed for performance surveillance and malfunction detection of hydrocyclones. Schlaberg et al. (2000) used Ultrasound Reflection Tomography to measure the size and position of the air core in a hydrocyclone. It is implied that the techniques can be used to control the input flow rate, to detect spigot wear, and to infer the separation efficiency by correlating these with the properties of the air core. Gutiérrez et al. (2000) utilized Electrical Impedance Tomography to identify the particle distribution and the air core size inside a hydrocyclone. Blockage of the underflow can be deduced by further analyzing the data and correlating the analyzed results with solid concentrations and blockage conditions. While tomographic methods are capable of indicating operational problems indirectly, the present study makes use of a medical PET scanner to clearly and directly identify anomalies during hydrocyclone operation.

1.3 Applying medical PET scanners for studying flow processes

PET, 3-D mapping the distribution of radioactive compounds for medical purposes, is a powerful imaging technique in medical sciences and clinics. In addition to their medical usages, PET scanners and cameras have been utilized for studying multi- or single-phase flows in various industrial processes by tracking a

point-like positron emitting source, i.e. the 'positron emission particle tracking' (PEPT) technique. For instance, Ingram et al. (2007) used a Philips/ADAC Forte camera to simultaneously track two particles in a fluidized bed for investigating the approach and separation of particles as bubbles pass and draw them into their wakes. Griffiths et al. (2008) used a Philips/ADAC Forte camera to study inclusion movement in steel castings.

Hoffmann et al. (2005) used a Siemens ECAT EXACT HR+ PET camera to follow a single particle in a fluidized bed with high temporal and spatial resolutions. The data output from the PET camera were deciphered and an algorithm for positioning the particle was developed, this study demonstrating the potential for using a PET camera to study a fast moving particles in the swirly and highly turbulent flow in hydrocyclones.

In this present work a Siemens TruePoint PET scanner was used to track a bead mimicking a solid particle being separated from water in a hydrocyclone.

2 EXPERIMENTS

The hydrocyclone, a modification of the geometry of the Stairmand high-efficiency cyclone, was incorporated in a recirculating flow system and placed in the PET scanner as shown in Figure 1 (b). Attached to the heavier-phase outlet is a particle collection chamber with an outflow control. An ^{18}F labelled resin bead was discharged into the flow loop close to and upstream of the hydrocyclone inlet. Particle labelling procedures and experimental details are described in (Chang et al., 2011a).

The approximate mean size of the beads is $630\ \mu\text{m}$, and the density of the beads in water is only slightly higher than that of water. Measurements of the settling velocity of the beads with sizes of $392\text{--}683\ \mu\text{m}$ in water in the field of gravity showed a settling velocity of $7.8\text{--}11.1\ \text{mm/s}$, which conforms that the dynamically equivalent diameters of the bead is above the cut size of the hydrocyclone, and thus the beads should be separated and collected in the collection chamber.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic showing the flow pattern and working principle of a reverse-flow cyclone with a cylinder-on-cone geometry. (b) A photo of the hydrocyclone (made by resin casting onto a metal mold) incorporated in a recirculating flow system and placed in the TruePoint PET scanner. Under the photo the inner dimensions of the cyclone used.

As the isotopes undergo a positive beta decay, a positron is generated, which annihilates with an electron within a few mm from the nucleus. The annihilation produces a pair of gamma photons propagating in opposite directions (in approximate 180 degree). When the gamma photon pair is detected, the particle is known to locate on the line, i.e. the line of response (LOR), drawn between the detector pair. Numerous gamma photon pairs being detected, the location of the particle can be deduced from a cross-triangulation algorithm.

3 DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The data output from the TruePoint scanner are in 64-bit list-mode format, where the detector pair information and temporal marks inserted into the data stream every one millisecond are recorded. The detector pair information are transformed into 3-D positions according to the detector arrangement of the PET scanner. An algorithm developed by Hoffmann et al. (2005) for eliminating the false and scattered data and calculating the optimized particle location has been adapted and refined in this work, making it both faster and more accurate. In order to examine the labelling method and the positioning algorithm, the standard deviations of 1000 positions, determined once per millisecond, of a stationary particle in water were found and determined to be below 0.17 mm in three axes for a case where the number of LORs detected in a ms was around 800 (Chang et al., 2011a). The temporal resolution can be increased to 0.5 ms or better for investigating faster movement changes by evenly dividing the ms data.

Figure 2 shows the trajectory of a particle in the hydrocyclone operated with 20% liquid flowing out through the outlet on the collection chamber ('underflow'). A position was determined once per millisecond. In the experiment shown in Figure 2, the particle, taking about 0.5 sec to enter the collection chamber, swirled through the hydrocyclone smoothly.

Figure 2. The trajectory of a particle in the hydrocyclone operated with 20% liquid flowing out through the outlet on the collection chamber. Each point represents a millisecond position. It took about 0.5 sec for the particle to travel from entrance to exit.

When the outlet on the collection chamber was closed and the only fluid outlet was the vortex finder (no underflow), a different trajectory was observed as shown in Figure 3, where the particle took about 1.5 sec to exit the cyclone body. The particle was drawn into the inner upward-flowing vortex a few times before the axial position marked by an arrow in Figure 3. In the subsequent section close to the collection chamber, the track becomes very dense because the particle was drawn into the inner vortex many times, flowing towards the vortex finder, only to be centrifuged out again. The particle took only 0.43 sec to reach the arrow mark, but spend about 1 sec in the lower section. It is clear that the particle has encountered difficulties while being transported close to the exit.

Figure 3. The trajectory of a particle in the hydrocyclone operated with total liquid flowing out through the vortex finder. It took about 1.5 sec for the particle to travel from entrance to exit.

In addition to recurrent flow reversals, investigating the dense-track section in Figure 3 shows another detrimental flow behaviour: the particle was transported at a much slower speed after passing a specific axial position. This is shown in Figure 4, where the trajectory during 0.48-1.33 sec, enclosed by the rectangle in Figure 3, is magnified. In this period the particle swirled into this section and suddenly started to flow in a

Figure 3, is magnified. In this period the particle swirled into this section and suddenly started to flow in a disorganized pattern at an axial position, which caused the particle to be drawn into the inner vortex and initiated repeated flow reversals. As escaping from this area, the particle regained its swirling motion but proceeded at a lower speed, which can be recognized by the successive positions being much closer spaced compared to those at the beginning of this section. As illustrated by the particle trajectory, the flow field has changed along the axial axis from the original swirl to a highly turbulent field, and then to a much weaker swirl.

Figure 4. The trajectory in the period of 0.48-1.33 sec in the rectangle-enclosed part of Figure 3. It shows that the particle was trapped by the strongly turbulent flow and then, after escaping, regained its swirling motion, but proceeded at a slower speed, as the successive positions being much closer spaced.

As mentioned, cyclones work as a result of a net centrifugal force exerted on the dense phase in the swirling stream. Adequate tangential velocity is important for the particles to be centrifuged out and separated from the inner reverse-flowing liquid. Insufficient tangential velocity and flow instability, which can transiently alter the tangential velocity, can weaken the centrifugal force and cause the particles being dragged into the inner vortex, increasing the residence time, invoking blockage, and lowering the separation efficiency. It is therefore important to study the radial, tangential, and axial velocity of the particle in order to gain a deeper understanding of this flow anomaly.

A programming code has been developed to locate the cyclone axis by minimizing the sum of the squares of the distances between a line and all the particle positions in the cyclone. The code, implemented in Fortran, transforms the Cartesian coordinates to cylindrical coordinates (r, θ, z) , and calculates the radial, tangential, and axial velocities. Figure 5 (a) and (b) are the trajectories in polar (r, θ) coordinates shown in Figures 2 and 3, respectively, verifying the axis-finding algorithm.

Figure 5. (a) and (b) show the polar $(r-\theta)$ plot of the particle trajectories from Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively.

The particle's radial position as a function of its axial position for the two cases with and without underflow are plotted in Figure 6 (a) and (b), respectively. The solid lines indicate the cyclone wall and the vortex finder. These plots show a significant increase in the frequency of the particle's appearance near a specific z-position in the case without underflow. Upstream of this location, the particle can be seen to swirl close to the wall most of the time. At this location, in contrast, the particle frequently rotates at a smaller radius, a behaviour likely to cause problems for the separation.

Figure 6. The r-z plot of a particle's ms positions. (a) corresponds to Figure 2 (20% underflow) and (b) to Figure 3 (no underflow). The r-axis is expanded.

The flow anomaly is further investigated by plotting the axial velocity as a function of axial position as shown in Figure 7. In the case with 20% underflow shown in Figure 7 (a), the particle flowed upward at only a few axial positions (shown by the negative axial velocity) and this lasted for a short time, while in the no-underflow case, the particle spent much more time in flowing upward towards the vortex finder, especially in the section close to the collection chamber. This upward flow can reach high speed (more than 3 m/s) at the axial position between 330-380 mm. After this section the upward flow still occurs but not at such high speed.

Figure 7. The axial velocity as a function of axial position. (a) the case with 20% underflow and (b) the no-underflow case.

How the tangential velocity changes along the cyclone axis is shown in Figure 8. That the tangential velocity abruptly decreases after the axial position of 330 mm as shown in Figure 8 (b) demonstrates the frequent flow reversals. Some uncommon high tangential velocity values (10-18 m/s) appearing in Figure 8 (b) are due to that the particle lost its regular swirling motion and flowed in an irregular pattern, which conforms to the observation in Figure 4.

Figure 8. The tangential velocity as a function of axial position. (a) the case with 20% underflow and (b) the no-underflow case.

The tangential velocity as a function of time can further pinpoint the time at which the particle reaches the anomalous section. As shown in Figure 9, the tangential velocity abruptly decreases and starts to fluctuate violently from about 0.48 sec to 1.3 sec. After this the particle can be seen to be transported at a very low speed until entering the collection chamber, the same phenomenon being observed in the trajectory in Figure 4.

Figure 9. The tangential velocity as a function of time for the case with no underflow.

The line in Figure 9 represents the smoothed values obtained using Savitzky-Golay filtering method performed on a series of 31 values with a polynomial order of 2 (Savitzky et al., 1964). This method is utilized to make clear the oscillatory features of the tangential velocity for further comparison with the axial velocity, which is, however, out of the scope of this paper.

The axial and tangential velocity reveal that the particle's rotation was affected by instabilities in the flow field, which are proven most likely attributed to a deleterious phenomenon in cyclones known as the 'end of the vortex' (see also Chang et al., 2011b).

4 CONCLUSION

In this study the PEPT technique employing a medical PET scanner makes it possible to identify a flow anomaly, together with its axial position and the time at which a particle enters it in a hydrocyclone. Comparing the particle paths and residence time under different operation conditions, the particles were found to spend much longer time in the hydrocyclone in some cases than in others. Studying the details of the trajectories shows that the particle, in the cases where the residence time was long (the no-underflow cases), took excursions around a specific axial position low in the cyclone, whereas in the shorter-residence-time cases (the cases with 20% underflow) the particle swirled through the hydrocyclone rather straightforwardly.

An algorithm determining the cyclone axis and converting the Cartesian particle positions to cylindrical (r , θ , z) coordinates, where the z -axis is the axial axis of the cyclone, was formulated and verified. The r - z plot of a particle's ms positions shows, in the longer-time case, which corresponded to operating the cyclone with no underflow, an abrupt increase in the frequency of the particle's appearance near a specific z -position. The anomalous axial and tangential velocities were clearly recognized as comparing v_z - z and v_θ - z plots between these two cases. The particle in the longer-residence-time case suffered from decreased tangential velocity and frequent flow reversals. The section where the higher reverse flow speed occurs indicates the location of the 'end of the vortex', after which the particle was transported at lower axial and tangential speeds. The time at which the particle enters the anomaly is identified by the time-series of tangential velocity.

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